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SCHOOL COUNSELLING SERVICE: A PANACEA TO ENHANCING THE STANDARD
OF PRIMARY EDUCATION IN NIGERIA

By

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Abstract

Primary education is no doubt the foundation for which all other forms of education are built on, as such is referred to as basic education. Ironically, Nigeria primary education system seems to be a nightmare to many youngsters, hence the need for school counselling service. This article presents school counselling service as a psychological assistance rendered to pupils to enable them achieve self-direction, self-knowledge and self-realization. To realize these objectives, the philosophy of primary education is tailored to work harmoniously with the five national goals (i.e a free and democratic society; a just egalitarian society; a united, strong and self-reliant nations; a great and dynamic economy; a land full of bright opportunities for all citizens). The policy implication of these goals for primary school counselling concerning persona-social problems of pupils are discussed. The paper further reviewed some theories applicable to primary school counselling practice. These include; Behavioural, Psychoanalysis, Rational Emotive, Eclectic and Client-centered theories. The article shows how school counselling service would enhance the standard of primary education in Nigeria. A major recommendation offered suggests the establishment of counselling units in all primary schools in Nigeria with professionally trained counsellors employed to render school counselling service.

Keywords: Primary School, Counselling Service, Standard Primary Education

Introduction

Primary education is part of the early education processes that lay the background for child development. It is a formal education system that begins at childhood and sometimes extend to early adolescence (6-12 years) (Egbo, 2015). It is no doubt a very significant period in the life of individuals. Consequently, teachers and parents of the kids join hands to nurture the mind of the child to a meaningful status. Human mind at this level is usually in a “tabular rasa” form. This implies that the mind of the child, at this level is virgin and open, needing to be filled up. Hence, the need to institute counselling service in primary school cannot be over emphasized. By virtues of good counselling and subsequent training, the youngster begins to develop positively.

School counselling takes care of the needs of the pupils to demonstrate adjustment and maturity in relationships and cushion possible discovery of their talents, abilities, potentialities, strengths and weakness at the earliest stages for their own betterment (Haruna, Ayo, Gambo & Muazu, 2012). The need to improve primary education makes it imperative that school counselling service should be established at the primary school level. The aim is to enhance early and positive adjustment procedures for meaningful living. The crux of this article is to highlight the panacea of school counselling service towards enhancing the standard of primary education in Nigeria. To comprehend the trend of thoughts of this article, the paper is presented in the following order:

Concept of School Counselling

Among the various services of guidance programme organized by educational institutions or schools ‘counselling service’ has a vital role to play. It is the most prominent aspect of guidance which conveys the meaning of guidance in different situations for different services (Saye, 2003). Most of the time, it is treated as synonym of guidance. That’s why it is regarded as the very core of the guidance programme. Usually counselling is given at many levels. It means in homes, parents counsel their children, in the clinic or hospital the doctor counsels the patient. In the court, the lawyer counsels the client. Like this in educational institutions or schools, teachers counsel their pupils as counsellors (Haruna, Ayo, Gambo & Muazu, 2012).

The term counselling in guidance literature conveys a meaning much more than its literary meaning and its scope is much broader than mere giving advice (Anameze, 2002). The major concern of counselling service is to help the individual to achieve self-direction, self-knowledge and self-realization (Haruna, Ayo, Gambo & Muazu, 2012). Counselling generally refers to a face-to-face meeting for interpersonal relationship of the counsellor and the counsellee in which the counsellor who happens to be person with special training and competency offers suggestions, opinion and advice to the counsellee to assist him (the counsellee) to understand himself and to develop his potentialities and resources so that he may function as an independent and self-reliant person, capable of making his own decisions and solving his own problems (Mearns, 1998). In other words, it can be stated as a consultancy service and through mutual exchange the counsellor can motivate the counsellee in bringing about changes in attitudes and in development of skills and competency and make right choices.

Nature of Primary Education

Primary education is the education given to children in the first six years of school (Orimidu, 2004). It is for the children between age 6 and 12. One may wonder why primary education is referred to as the first years of schooling when children had already attended the nursery and kindergarten schools before being admitted into a primary school. Again both the nursery/kindergarten schools are usually referred to as pre-school, which means before formal education. Formal education begins with primary education, which is the foundation of all the education systems (National Policy on Education, 2013). As a foundation, its quality will determine the quality of the rest of it. In fact, primary education is the substructure upon which other education levels are created.

Philosophy of Nigerian Education

A nation's policy on education is government's way of realizing that part of the national goals which can be achieved, using education as a tool. No policy on education can be formulated without first identifying the philosophy and goals of the nation. The philosophy of Nigerian education is embedded in the National Policy on Education (NPE). According to the policy document (NPE, 2013), the five national goals which Nigeria's philosophy of education draws its strength are: a free and, democratic society; a just egalitarian society; a united, strong and self-reliant nations; a great and dynamic economy; a land full of bright opportunities for all citizens. Based on the above national aspirations (NPE, 2013), the philosophy of the Nigerian education seeks to: develop the individual into a sound and effective citizen; full integration of the individual into the community; and provision of equal access to educational opportunities for all citizens of the country at the primary, secondary and tertiary levels both inside and outside the formal school system.

In order to make the philosophy of education work harmoniously for Nigeria's goals, education in the country has to be tailored towards self-realization, right human relations, individual and national efficiency, effective citizenship, national consciousness, national unity as well as towards social, cultural, economic, political, scientific and technological progress (NPE, 2013).

Policy implications for Primary School Counselling Service

In line with the foregoing policy (NPE, 2013), there is no doubt that primary school pupils experience a number of problems in the school and at home, relating to their adjustment, educational choice and occupational choice etc which are central to the attainment of the goals spelt out in the document. But most of their problems are of personal-social in nature (Sambo, 2008). These personal-social problems include: change of subject; proper study habits; feelings of inferiority; free studentship and concession; getting along with one's peers; preparing for the examination; manners and morals (Abdullahi, 2003). Therefore primary school pupils need counselling services to enable them know how they should deal with or tackle the problems they are facing in their daily life situations. Sometimes a pupil is unaware that he has a problem, unless he is made to be aware of his problems, he can't be helped in his development (Saye, 2003). For this he requires counselling to develop insight into his problems. Besides, it has been observed that a pupil needs a wise and sympathetic person to whom he can talk about his personal problems (Shertzer & Stone, 1980), a person who can give a patient hearing to his problems and assist him to solve his problems (Abdullahi, 2003). The counselling session provides this opportunity to the

pupils to talk about their problems and develop insight into the possible solutions to the problems they encounter.

Some School Counselling Theories applicable to primary school

1. Behavioural theory traces pupil's development and assumes that an individual at birth has a neutral character, which means they possess behaviour that cannot be said to be good or bad (Bandura, Barbaranelli, Laprara & Pastorell, 2001). Pupils shape or pattern of behaviour has to be moulded by the interaction of their hereditary traits and their environments. This interaction is known as the learning process (Skinner, 1953).

Undesirable or deviant behaviours are learnt and can also be unlearned. However, socially appropriate behaviour can be learnt to replace inappropriate ones (Haruna, Ayo, Gambo & Muazu, 2012). Proponents of this viewpoint propose some school counselling techniques which include: shaping, extinction, reinforcing incompatible behaviours, cognitive learning, covert reinforcement and contracting (Bandura, Barbaranelli, Laprara & Pastorell, 2001).

2. Psychoanalysts are of the view that human beings are controlled by a strong biological force called libido which is also known as sexual drive (Freud, 1959). According to the viewpoint, this driving force in human beings makes pupils think and behave the way they do. Freud also agreed that the forces or impulses are always in conflict with other forces in the environment thereby leading to constraints and strains that render the individual emotionally disturbed. The individual will continue to strive to overcome the constraints, resolve the conflict and satisfy his own needs. This conflict with the environment may hinder the individual desires or redirect them or even completely denying the individual of satisfying or accomplishing his needs.
3. The eclectic theorists assumes that the individual is too complex and vast to be adequately understood and helped by one theory, rather, combination of appropriate methods from various sources or theories with compatible features should be selected to help the counsellee (Tolbert, 1994). In other words, useful elements in all theories, techniques and procedures in all theories should be used to treat a client. This theory does not on its own contain any specific theory of personality development.
4. Rational Emotive Therapy of Albert Ellis seeks to help counsellee solve their problems by focusing on their cognitive processes (National Career Development Association, 2003). The rational approach holds that most problems of counsellee are connected with their process reasoning and thinking. It means that for them to change their behaviour, their cognitive process would first of all change, and when this change occurs in their cognitive process, it creates a tension in their belief system which results in change in behaviour (Rokench, 1973). The rational theorists believe that the cause or causes of counsellee problems should first of all be diagnosed, which has to do with testing and analyzing a wide range of data obtained from the counsellee so as to be able to identify the real cause.
5. Client centered-centered counselling developed by Rogers (1951), is based on the belief that problems originate from emotional blocks or conflicts and that people already have the necessary objective knowledge for deciding what should be done about their problems. In this counselling approach, the client or student is actively involved in the counselling

relationship. He or she talks much about the problems, suggests way to solve the problem and carries out the ways arrived at by both of them (Mearns, 1994). Carl Rogers strongly had faith, in human beings having the ability to always do good only if certain conditions in the environment are present to assist them. This means that Carl Rogers does not believe that human beings need expert direction from anybody before they can do what is good. What the individual needs most is a conducive environment in which every body trusts and respects each other (Mearns & Thorne, 1998).

School counselling service as a panacea to improving the standard of primary education

Primary school counselling service establishes a trusting, accepting, safe and sharing relationship with the pupils (Egbochuku, 2008) thereby encourages them to express their worries and problems such that they can develop insight into their real problems and to assist them in self-understanding and self-development (Ipaye, 2005). It is in this sense that counselling is developmental in nature. In addition, counselling service in primary school assists the pupil to understand the factors which have caused their problems, worries and difficulties and be alert about those factors so as to be able to prevent the recurrence of his problems and difficulties (Okorobia & Okorodudu, 2004). In this sense, counselling is preventive in nature.

School counselling assists primary school pupils to understand themselves and their environment and to find out solutions to their problems with satisfaction to themselves and benefit to the environment (Oladele, 2000). Finding solution to pupils' problems leads to emotional release and reassurance. Since problem solving is an aspect of human life, no one can claim to be free from all problems. Therefore the goal of school counselling is to help someone overcome such problem that may come his way.

School Counselling seeks to improve personal effectiveness of pupils so that they can commit themselves to activities or personal projects, by investing time and energy and be able to take appropriate vocational, psychological and physical risks (Abdullahi, 2003). Counselling helps someone gain knowledge about himself, his abilities, capabilities and his environment. By gaining knowledge of oneself, an individual is able to explore opportunities available in his environment leading to self-actualization and self-worth (Haruna, Ayo, Gambo & Muazu, 2012).

Counselling focuses on the mechanism of change brought about by physiological and psychological development in clients (Saye, 2003). The counsellee should therefore be assisted in the process of change which pervade the period of adolescence through early adulthood during which the client is helped to realize his potentials. This goal seeks to develop in individual the ability to make decision about one's life. Decision making help to foster personal growth as it is the ultimate goal of counselling (Abdullahi, 2003).

Conclusion

School counselling service is nothing but job aspects where counsellors exhibit specialized dispensation of their jobs. Thus, all forms of counselling expertise are applied at the primary school level to bring the best in the school kids. Unfortunately, focus and emphases are placed on the secondary and tertiary levels in school counselling, instead of the primary stage where the pupils are at the formative stages of their character.

The primary school pupils encounter problems from sexual abuse, lateness to school, truancy, cheating at home and in schools, bullying, fighting, withdrawal problems, day dreaming, poor study habits, among others. If counselling is properly applied to stem these problems at the

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formative stages, the kids will experience less adjustment problems, even in subsequent stages of their lives. This explains the need for school counselling at the primary level. As a result, all stake holders in education in Nigeria, should join hands to encourage and invest in crucial counselling service at the primary school level to avert maladjustment problems at the secondary and tertiary levels in later stages of life.

Recommendations

1. Government should establish counselling unit in all primary schools in Nigeria with professionally trained counsellor employed to render school counselling services.
2. School administrators should be sensitized on the functions and relevance of school counsellors and the need for collaboration with each other.
3. Parents' Teachers' Association (PTA) should be made to partly fund school counselling programmes.
4. Workshops and seminars should be regularly organized for teachers in order to acquaint them with rudiments of counselling practice.
5. Pupils should be encouraged to patronize school counselling services.

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